

INTERACTIVE EFFECTS OF WEED CONTROL AND FERTILIZER MANAGEMENT ON GROWTH OF FARO RICE VARIETIES IN LOWLAND ECOSYSTEMS OF ABUJA, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) remains a vital staple for over half of the world's population, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa, where lowland rice sustains food security and rural livelihoods. However, productivity in these systems is often constrained by weed competition and suboptimal nutrient management. This study investigated the interactive effects of weed management regimes and fertilizer types on three lowland rice varieties (FARO 44, FARO 57, and FARO 60) under field conditions in Abuja, Nigeria. A split-split plot design was used, comprising three fertilizer treatments (organic, inorganic, and no fertilizer) and four weed management options (standard herbicide rate, reduced herbicide rate, manual weeding, and no weeding), resulting in 12 treatment combinations. Growth parameters including plant height, tiller number, leaf number, leaf area index (LAI), root traits, biomass, and relative growth rate (RGR) were evaluated over two consecutive rainy seasons (2023 and 2024). FARO 60 significantly ($p < 0.05$) exhibited superior vegetative growth including plant heights, root numbers, root length, LAI values and biomass. Conversely, FARO 44 produced the highest tiller (6.49; 6.48) and leaf numbers (9.78) across years. Among management practices, reduced herbicide rate without fertilizer (M2F3), standard herbicide rate with inorganic fertilizer (M1F2), and reduced herbicide rate with inorganic fertilizer (M2F2) consistently enhanced growth. Overall, the findings emphasize that varietal selection combined with integrated weed and nutrient management is crucial for optimizing lowland rice productivity.

Keywords: FARO varieties, nutrient management, reduced herbicide, sustainable farming, weed management

INTRODUCTION

Rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) remains a pivotal food crop globally, providing sustenance to more than half of the world's population (Jabeen *et al.*, 2023). In sub-Saharan Africa, particularly in Nigeria, the demand for rice has steadily increased due to population growth, urbanization, and dietary shifts (Ngwoke *et al.*, 2025). Among the various production ecologies, lowland rice systems hold significant potential due to their relatively stable water supply and higher yield capacity compared to upland systems (Raj *et al.*, 2017). However, rice productivity in these systems remains sub-optimal, primarily due to poor weed management and declining soil fertility (Connor *et al.*, 2023; Dossou-Yovo *et al.*, 2022). Weeds are among the most significant biological constraints to rice production, especially in lowland ecologies (Duary *et al.*, 2015). They compete aggressively with rice for light, nutrients, space, and water, especially during the early stages of crop development. Yield losses due to weed interference in lowland rice have been estimated to range from 30% to 80%, depending on the duration and intensity of weed infestation (Dass *et al.*, 2017; Kaur *et al.*, 2018). Effective weed control strategies are therefore indispensable for optimizing crop performance. Commonly adopted weed management practices include manual weeding, chemical herbicides, and integrated approaches (Kumar *et al.*, 2023). While manual weeding remains prevalent among smallholder farmers due to cost considerations (Sims *et al.*, 2018), it is labor-intensive and often untimely (Woyessa, 2022). Conversely, herbicides offer efficiency but raise concerns related to resistance development, environmental contamination, and health hazards (Parven

et al., 2025). Simultaneously, soil nutrient depletion continues to limit rice productivity in many lowland systems (Suriyagoda, 2022). Fertilizer application is a principal strategy for restoring soil fertility and enhancing crop growth (Shah and Wu, 2019). However, the type and source of fertilizer significantly influence nutrient use efficiency, soil health, and environmental sustainability (Roy, 2021). Inorganic fertilizers provide readily available nutrients but are often linked to soil acidification and long-term fertility decline (Pahalvi *et al.*, 2021). Organic fertilizers, such as poultry manure or compost, improve soil structure and microbial activity but release nutrients slowly (Singh *et al.*, 2020; Shajiet *et al.*, 2021). Integrated nutrient management, which combines organic and inorganic sources, is increasingly promoted as a sustainable approach that enhances crop productivity while preserving soil integrity (Bhatt *et al.*, 2019). The interaction between fertilizer regimes and weed management strategies is of particular interest (Kumar *et al.*, 2024), as nutrient availability can affect crop competitiveness against weeds, while weed pressure can modulate nutrient uptake and biomass allocation (Kaur, *et al.*, 2018; Little *et al.*, 2021). Moreover, the response to these agronomic practices may vary across rice varieties due to differences in morphology, growth duration, and resource use efficiency (Dass *et al.*, 2017; Kaur, *et al.*, 2018).

Despite extensive research on weed management and fertilizer application in rice production, most studies have examined these factors independently rather than their combined effects in lowland systems. Limited information exists on how different fertilizer sources

interact with weed management strategies to influence rice growth and yield. Additionally, variations among rice genotypes in response to these combined agronomic practices remain poorly understood. Therefore, this research is needed to evaluate the interactive effects of weed management, fertilizer regimes, and rice genotypes to develop effective and sustainable management strategies for lowland rice production. This study aims to evaluate the growth performance of three lowland rice varieties as influenced by weed management strategies and fertilizer types. Specifically, it seeks to: (i) assess the combined effects of fertilizer types (organic, inorganic, and no fertilizer) and weed control methods (standard herbicide rate, reduced herbicide rate, manual weeding and no weeding) on rice growth attributes; (ii) determine varietal differences in growth response under different treatment combinations; and (iii) provide agronomically and environmentally sound recommendations to enhance lowland rice productivity in West African conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Description of Experimental Site and Conditions

The study was conducted at the Teaching and Research Farm within the Faculty of Agriculture, University of Abuja. This location is situated in Abuja and is characterized by a tropical savanna climate, marked by clearly defined rainy and dry seasons. The experimental field is positioned at an altitude between 360 and 490 meters above sea level. The region typically receives annual rainfall ranging from 1,200 mm to 1,500 mm, with the

majority falling between April and October. During the rainy season, temperatures generally range from 22°C to 30°C (NiMet, 2021). The soil in the area is classified as sandy loam, consisting of 71% sand, 14% silt, and 15% clay, with a slightly acidic pH of 6.5 and a carbon content of 9.8 g/kg according to the soil analysis conducted at the Soil Science Laboratory, University of Uyo, Nigeria. Prior to setting up the experiment, the land was left uncultivated for a year to promote consistent soil conditions and eliminate the influence of previous agricultural activities.

Experimental Treatments and Design

The experiment was laid out in a split-split plot arrangement with three replications, to examine the influence of weed management regimes and fertilizer types on the growth performance of three upland rice varieties. The main plot factor (Rice varieties): FARO 44, FARO 57, and FARO 60. These varieties were selected based on their favourable agronomic characteristics and adaptability to lowland rice-growing conditions in the region. The sub-plot factor (Weed management): standard rate of Agricore herbicide (500 ml ha⁻¹), reduced rate of Agricore herbicide (300 ml ha⁻¹), manual weeding using a hand hoe at critical growth stages, and an untreated control with no weed management. The sub-sub plot factor (Fertilizer types): organic fertilizer, inorganic fertilizer (NPK 15-15-15) and no-fertilizer (control). These treatments were factorially combined to create twelve distinct management regimes: M1F1 (standard herbicide rate and organic fertilizer), M1F2 (standard herbicide rate and inorganic fertilizer), M1F3 (standard herbicide rate and no fertilizer), M2F1 (reduced herbicide rate

and organic fertilizer), M2F2 (reduced herbicide rate and inorganic fertilizer), M2F3 (reduced herbicide rate and no fertilizer), M3F1 (manual weeding and organic fertilizer), M3F2 (manual weeding and inorganic fertilizer), M3F3 (manual weeding and no fertilizer), M4F1 (no weeding and organic fertilizer), M4F2 (no weeding and inorganic fertilizer), and M4F3 (no weeding and no fertilizer). The total experimental area measured 259 m², consisting of 108 plots, small experimental plots (1 m x 1 m) were adopted due to land limitations and were separated with 0.5 m buffer zones to minimize edge effects and treatment interference while 1 m alleys were provided between blocks and between different rice varieties to ensure ease of access and experimental independence. This design enabled the evaluation of interaction effects of variety, weed management strategy, and fertilizer type on rice growth performance under lowland field condition.

Farming techniques

The field site was cleared of existing vegetation through a combination of manual labour and mechanical tools to remove weeds, grasses, and plant debris. This step was crucial to minimize weed interference and facilitate efficient tillage operations. Land preparation involved a two-stage tillage process. The primary tillage was carried out using a tractor-mounted moldboard plow to a depth of 20–25 cm, helping to break compacted soil, incorporate organic materials, and enhance soil aeration and drainage. This was followed by secondary tillage using a harrow, applied twice at one-week intervals to further break down soil clods and achieve a fine, uniform seedbed. A leveling

board was then used to smooth the surface, ensuring even water distribution and proper planting conditions. The field was then divided into experimental plots based on the design layout: main plots were assigned to different rice varieties, sub-plots to weed management practices, and sub-sub plots to fertilizer treatments. Each plot was clearly marked and labeled to ensure precise data collection and plot management. Sowing took place on July 21, 2023 and July 22, 2024 using the manual dibbling method, where three seeds were sown per hole at a depth of 2 cm with a spacing of 20 cm × 20 cm to ensure ideal plant density. At three weeks after sowing, thinning was done to retain one seedling per hill. Manual sowing was used to ensure uniform placement.

Three fertilizer treatments: organic, inorganic, and control (no fertilizer) were evaluated for their influence on rice growth. The organic fertilizer HELIN-1-FARM, a liquid formulation, was applied at a total rate of 6 L ha⁻¹, split into two applications. It was diluted at a ratio of 1 L of fertilizer to 48 L of water and applied at 3 and 8 weeks after sowing (WAS). NPK (15:15:15) was applied at 200 kg ha⁻¹ to supply approximately 60 kg N, 60 kg P₂O₅ and 60 kg K₂O ha⁻¹ 3 WAS, followed by 65 kg ha⁻¹ of urea at 8 WAS. Control plots received no fertilizer to serve as a reference. Herbicide was applied 4 WAS, after which weed control was maintained according to the treatment specifications using Agriforce, a post-emergence selective herbicide containing bispyribac-sodium (100 g L⁻¹). Agriforce was applied at 500 ml ha⁻¹ for the standard rate and 300 ml ha⁻¹ for the reduced rate. Manual weeding was implemented where required, while control plots were left unmanaged to allow natural

weed growth. At maturity, rice was harvested manually using a sickle, cutting the tillers about 10 cm above ground once grains had reached a golden-brown colour indicating full ripeness. Soil samples were taken both before planting and after harvest to assess nutrient status and pH. Five samples were collected from the top 15 cm using a soil auger and then combined into composite samples, which were analyzed following standard laboratory protocols.

Data Collection

Data on plant height, number of tillers, number of leaves, leaf area index (LAI), root count, root length, biomass and relative growth rate, were collected at 4, 8, and 12 weeks after sowing (WAS). Growth parameters were assessed following the standard protocols outlined by the International Rice Research Institute (IRRI, 2002). The collected data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) using SPSS version 27 to determine treatment effects. A split-split plot design was employed to evaluate interaction effects. Treatment means were compared using Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at a 5% level of significance. Significant treatment differences and interaction effects were assessed to understand the combined impact of rice varieties, weed management strategies, and fertilizer types.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Over the two-growing experimental period, FARO 60 consistently exhibited superior plant height relative to FARO 44, attaining mean values of 59.80 cm in 2023 and 61.20 cm in 2024. This observed advantage may be attributed to its enhanced capacity for vegetative growth under favourable

environmental conditions, which aligns with reports that varietal differences significantly influence plant height under optimal nutrient and management regimes (Islam *et al.*, 2019). In contrast, FARO 44 consistently produced the highest number of tillers, recording 6.49 and 6.48 tillers per plant in 2023 and 2024, respectively. This underscores its strong tillering ability and suggests a genetic predisposition for prolific tiller production, a trait widely recognized as a key determinant of yield potential in rice (Zhong *et al.*, 2003). With respect to leaf production, FARO 44 also maintained superiority across both years, with a stable mean of 9.78 leaves per plant. This consistency reflects a vigorous vegetative growth phase and suggests sustained assimilate production capacity during early development, which is often associated with improved canopy establishment (Jahan *et al.*, 2017). However, FARO 57 and FARO 60 significantly outperformed FARO 44 in terms of leaf area index (LAI) across both years. The higher LAI observed in these varieties indicates a greater photosynthetic surface area, which enhances light interception and biomass accumulation, thereby contributing to increased productivity potential (Zhao *et al.*, 2024).

Among treatments, reduced herbicide rate without fertilizer (M2F3) produced the tallest plants, although its superiority was less distinct in 2024. This pattern suggests that specific combinations of weed management and nutrient regimes can create favourable growth conditions, though their relative effectiveness may vary across seasons (Onwuchekwa-Henry *et al.*, 2022). The combination of standard herbicide rate and inorganic fertilizer (M1F2) consistently resulted in the highest tiller numbers, likely due to improved weed

control and nutrient availability (Awan *et al.*, 2015). Plots without weed management but with organic fertilizer (M4F1) recorded the highest leaf numbers, highlighting the role of nutrient supply in vegetative growth (Wu *et al.*, 2021). While LAI showed no significant treatment differences in 2023, variation emerged in 2024, with M3F3

recording the highest value, emphasizing the importance of integrated management strategies (Hashimoto *et al.*, 2023). Significant interaction effects between variety and treatment were observed, influencing tiller number and leaf traits in both years, and LAI in 2024 ($p \leq 0.05$) (Table 1).

Table 1: Influence of weed management strategies and fertilizer types on plant height, number of tillers, number of leaf and leaf area index per plant of three lowland rice cultivars

Variables	PH (cm)		TN		LN		LAI	
	2023	2024	2023	2024	2023	2024	2023	2024
Variety								
FARO 44	55.87 ^b	59.03 ^b	6.49 ^a	6.48 ^a	9.78 ^a	9.78 ^a	10.18 ^b	10.79 ^b
FARO 57	57.58 ^{ab}	60.12 ^a	5.88 ^b	6.01 ^b	8.64 ^b	8.78 ^b	12.76 ^a	13.34 ^a
FARO 60	59.80 ^a	61.20 ^a	5.78 ^c	5.85 ^c	8.56 ^b	8.50 ^c	12.91 ^a	13.36 ^a
SEM±	1.09	0.35	0.04	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.43	0.03
Treatment								
M1F1	55.87 ^{ab}	58.30 ^{cde}	6.30 ^a	6.33 ^a	9.07 ^{abc}	9.13 ^c	11.32	11.81 ^g
M2F1	57.62 ^{ab}	59.90 ^{bcd}	6.12 ^{abc}	6.27 ^b	9.00 ^{bcd}	9.07 ^c	11.22	11.79 ^g
M3F1	54.69 ^{ab}	57.36 ^{de}	5.93 ^{cde}	6.03 ^e	9.07 ^{abc}	9.06 ^c	11.68	12.21 ^f
M4F1	54.30 ^{ab}	56.83 ^{de}	5.93 ^{cde}	6.02 ^e	9.22 ^a	9.27 ^a	12.05	12.64 ^d
M1F2	59.03 ^{ab}	61.07 ^{abc}	6.04 ^{abcd}	6.08 ^d	9.15 ^{ab}	8.99 ^e	12.32	12.99 ^c
M2F2	53.14 ^b	55.36 ^e	6.15 ^{abc}	6.28 ^b	8.85 ^d	8.79 ^{ef}	11.28	11.85 ^{fg}
M3F2	57.69 ^{ab}	59.97 ^{bcd}	6.00 ^{bcde}	6.15 ^c	8.85 ^d	8.75 ^f	11.5 ^l	12.04 ^{fg}
M4F2	59.98 ^{ab}	62.36 ^{ab}	6.22 ^{ab}	5.13 ^f	8.81 ^d	8.80 ^{def}	11.28	11.78 ^g
M1F3	59.35 ^{ab}	61.89 ^{abc}	6.00 ^{bcde}	6.04 ^e	8.89 ^{cd}	8.99 ^e	12.02	12.61 ^{de}
M2F3	61.33 ^a	63.96 ^a	5.78 ^e	5.92 ^f	9.00 ^{bcd}	9.04 ^{bc}	12.81	13.38 ^b
M3F3	60.40 ^{ab}	62.30 ^{ab}	5.85 ^{de}	5.92 ^f	9.15 ^{ab}	9.09 ^b	13.31	13.93 ^a
M4F3	59.61 ^{ab}	62.32 ^{ab}	6.00 ^{bcde}	5.92 ^f	8.89 ^{cd}	9.12 ^{abc}	12.6	12.99 ^{cd}
SEM±	2.19	0.69	0.07	0.01	0.07	0.04	0.86	0.07
V x T	Ns	Ns	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	0.03	Ns	0.01

Mean value of figures with the same superscript in a column are not significantly different ($p < 0.05$). Plant height=PH, tiller number=TN, leaf number= LN, leaf area index=LAI.

Across the two-growing seasons, FARO 60 consistently recorded the highest root number (33.34 in 2023 and 34.02 in 2024), while FARO 57 and FARO 44 exhibited statistically similar but lower values, underscoring genotypic variation in root system development and its implications for nutrient uptake (*Ju et al.*, 2015). Root length was comparable between FARO 57 and FARO 60 and significantly greater than FARO 44 in 2023, but no varietal differences were observed in 2024, suggesting environmental modulation of root traits (*Xin et al.*, 2021). Biomass production was consistently higher in FARO 57 and FARO 60, both significantly outperforming FARO 44, reflecting superior assimilate accumulation linked to enhanced root systems (*Barison & Uphoff*, 2011). However, relative growth rate (RGR) remained similar across varieties, indicating comparable growth efficiency despite morphological differences (*Quazi et al.*, 2011).

Among treatments, reduced herbicide rate with inorganic fertilizer (M2F2) produced the highest root numbers, whereas manual weeding with organic fertilizer (M3F1) recorded the lowest, highlighting the importance of integrated weed and nutrient management in root development (*Awan et al.*, 2015). Root length was greatest under reduced herbicide with no fertilizer (M2F3), though differences were only significant in 2023, suggesting inconsistent seasonal effects (*Zhang & Webster*, 2002). Biomass did not differ among treatments in 2023, but M4F3 recorded the highest value in 2024, possibly due to compensatory growth under low-input conditions (*Klinsawang et al.*, 2018). Nevertheless, RGR remained unaffected by treatments in both years, indicating stable growth efficiency across management practices (*Quazi et al.*, 2011) (Table 2).

Table 2: Influence of weed management strategies and fertilizer types on number of roots, root length, biomass and relative growth rate per plant of three lowland rice cultivars

Variables	RN		RL (cm)		BM(g)		RGR	
	2023	2024	2023	2024	2023	2024	2023	2024
Variety								
FARO 44	24.67 ^b	25.52 ^b	5.61 ^b	6.03	2.12 ^b	2.22 ^b	0.01	0.01
FARO 57	25.63 ^b	26.00 ^b	6.00 ^a	6.12	2.16 ^a	2.26 ^a	0.01	0.01
FARO 60	33.34 ^a	34.04 ^a	6.27 ^a	6.35	2.22 ^a	2.39 ^a	0.01	0.01
SEM±	1.14	0.29	0.14	0.08	0.11	0.03	0.01	0.01
Treatment								
M1F1	25.56 ^{ab}	27.17 ^{cd}	6.00 ^{ab}	6.17 ^{abc}	2.01	2.12 ^b	0.01	0.02
M2F1	25.56 ^{ab}	27.17 ^{bcd}	5.70 ^{ab}	5.91 ^{bc}	2.07	2.16 ^b	0.01	0.01
M3F1	26.07 ^b	25.69 ^d	5.89 ^{ab}	6.07 ^{abc}	2.08	2.18 ^b	0.01	0.01
M4F1	27.14 ^{ab}	27.83 ^{bcd}	6.04 ^{ab}	6.24 ^{abc}	2.15	2.23 ^b	0.01	0.01
M1F2	26.67 ^{ab}	27.43 ^{cd}	5.93 ^{ab}	6.12 ^{abc}	2.11	2.21 ^b	0.01	0.01
M2F2	34.11 ^a	34.79 ^a	5.88 ^{ab}	6.08 ^{abc}	2.19	2.27 ^b	0.01	0.01
M3F2	26.96 ^{ab}	27.82 ^{bcd}	5.42 ^b	5.59 ^c	2.14	2.25 ^b	0.02	0.01
M4F2	26.59 ^{ab}	27.48 ^{bcd}	6.05 ^{ab}	6.30 ^{abc}	2.19	2.29 ^b	0.01	0.01
M1F3	27.33 ^{ab}	27.98 ^{bcd}	5.78 ^{ab}	5.96 ^{bc}	2.02	2.12 ^b	0.01	0.01
M2F3	28.78 ^{ab}	29.54 ^{bc}	6.45 ^a	6.73 ^a	2.18	2.29 ^b	0.01	0.01
M3F3	28.92 ^{ab}	29.79 ^b	6.28 ^{ab}	6.54 ^{ab}	2.17	2.29 ^b	0.01	0.01
M4F3	28.85 ^{ab}	29.35 ^{bc}	6.14 ^{ab}	6.28 ^{abc}	2.93	3.06 ^a	0.01	0.01
SEM±	2.29	0.57	0.27	0.17	0.22	0.05	0.00	0.02
V x T	Ns	Ns	Ns	Ns	Ns	Ns	Ns	Ns

Mean value of figures with the same superscript in a column are not significantly different ($p < 0.05$). Root number=RN, root length=RL, biomass=BM, relative growth rate=RGR.

Over the two-year study period, FARO 44 consistently demonstrated superior tiller production across all treatment combinations. In 2023, its estimated tiller numbers ranged from 6.3 to 6.7, increasing slightly in 2024 to 6.3–7.0, highlighting its stable performance and minimal sensitivity to variations in weed management and fertilizer inputs. Peak tillering occurred under M3F2 and M4F2 in 2024, suggesting that organic fertilizer (F2) combined with

manual or no weed control strategies positively influenced tiller formation. In contrast, FARO 57 exhibited a moderate but more variable response. Tiller numbers in 2023 ranged from 5.0 to 6.1, with a noticeable drop under M3F2, indicating a potentially adverse interaction between manual weeding (M3) and inorganic fertilizer. This trend continued in 2024, where values fluctuated between 5.2 and 6.5 again dipping at M3F2 but improving

under M4F2, implying that delayed weed control (M4) may mitigate earlier stress effects. FARO 60 proved to be the most input-sensitive, showing a consistent decline in tiller number across both years. In 2023, tiller counts dropped from 6.2 under M1F1 to ≤ 5.0 under M2F3 to M4F3, reflecting a negative response to no fertilizer (F3) and late or aggressive weed control. A similar pattern was observed in

2024: while initial performance under M1F1 to M4F2 was comparable to FARO 44 and 57, a sharp drop occurred from M1F3 onward, with values stabilizing around 5.0 through M4F3. This highlights FARO 60's high sensitivity to no fertilizer, likely compounded by late-season weed pressure (see Figures 1).

Figure 1: Interaction Effects of Variety, Weed Management Strategy, and Fertilizer Type on Tiller Number in 2023 and 2024. Error bars represent standard errors

Across the two-year study period (2023–2024), clear genotypic variations in leaf number were observed in response to different fertilizer and weed management treatments. FARO 44 consistently recorded the highest leaf counts (~9.5–10.0), demonstrating minimal fluctuation and strong stability across treatments, especially in 2024. FARO 57 produced moderate leaf numbers (8.0–9.2), with a gradual decline from M1F1 to M4F2,

followed by an increase at M3F3, suggesting a delayed favorable response to no fertilizer under manual weeding. FARO 60 started with the lowest leaf numbers (~8.0 at M1F1) but showed a steady increase, reaching a peak near 9.0 at M3F2–M3F3, before declining at M4F3, indicating potential sensitivity to intensive input combinations which is no weed management and no fertilizer application (see Figures 2).

Figure 2: Interaction Effects of Variety, Weed Management Strategy, and Fertilizer Type on Leaf Number in 2023 and 2024. Error bars represent standard errors

The interaction of varieties and treatment for Leaf Area Index (LAI) reveals distinct varietal responses to combinations of weed control and fertilizer inputs. FARO 57 maintained the highest and most consistent LAI values (13.0–14.5), indicating strong vegetative growth and adaptability. In contrast, FARO 44 showed lower and more variable LAI (~8.5–12.5), with noticeable

peaks at M1F2, M2F3, and M3F3, suggesting its growth is more affected by input timing and competition. FARO 60 demonstrated high but fluctuating LAI, reaching up to 14.7 at M1F3 and M3F2, but dropping below 11.0 at M2F2, reflecting its dependence on optimized management conditions (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Interaction Effects of Variety, Weed Management Strategy, and Fertilizer Type on Leaf Area Index in 2024.

Error bars represent standard errors

CONCLUSION

The study demonstrated that varietal differences significantly influence growth responses to weed and fertilizer management in lowland rice systems. FARO 60 exhibited superior vegetative performance in terms of plant height, leaf area index, root number, root length, and biomass, while FARO 44 showed greater tillering and leaf production capacity. The integration of effective weed control with appropriate fertilizer management further enhanced overall crop performance, underscoring the importance of combining suitable genotypes with optimal

agronomic practices.

Based on these findings, FARO 60 is recommended for achieving improved growth and biomass accumulation, whereas FARO 44 is more suitable where enhanced tillering and leaf development are desired. Additionally, treatment combinations such as M2F3, M1F1, and M2F2 are recommended due to their consistent effectiveness in promoting optimal growth. Future research should focus on refining integrated weed and nutrient management strategies to further enhance rice productivity across different varieties.

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